

EVALUATION OF DETECTION METHODS ON INSECT VECTOR *PHILAENUS SPUMARIUS* BY INTRALABORATORY AND INTERLABORATORY COMPARISON TESTS.

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Recently detected in Italy, France, Germany and Spain, the bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* (Xf) attacks many wild and cultivated plant species. It is transmitted and carried by xylem-sap feeder insects. Only a few groups of Hemipteran, all belonging to the suborder Auchenorrhyncha, are known to be effective vectors of the disease. They are mainly leafhoppers, spittlebugs, aphrophorids and cicadas. To date, only *Philaenus spumarius* has been identified as the main efficient vector insect in Italy. In France it has been detected positive for the presence of Xf when collected in outbreaks areas of Corsica and French Riviera. In the context of the emergence of Xf in France and the epidemiological surveillance of this bacterium, work targeting insects has been conducted by ANSES Plant Health Laboratory since 2016. A method of detection by real time PCR has been optimized and validated on individual *Philaenus spumarius*. Performance criteria of the method (analytical sensitivity, specificity, repeatability, reproducibility) were evaluated on spike insect crushing's. An interlaboratory test performance study proposed in parallel by ANSES in the framework of the H2020 POnTE and EUPHRESKO PROMODE projects permitted to evaluate available and practiced methods within the network of European partners (20 participant laboratories) on naturally positive insects and spiked insect crushing's. Moreover the performance of the method on groups of insects is currently evaluated. The updated results will be presented.